

THE CREATION OF PARTICULAR LEARNING METHODS FOR BLIND CHILDREN

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Abstract: The aim of the research is to provide a disseminate view on the methods for learning for visually impaired children. The economic factors along with psycho-social aspects have impacted blind education in India. Due to the lesser number of population, not impacting much on the productivity of the state, visually impaired children suffer the consequence of social and political ignorance leading to incomplete education and illiteracy. The current research is based on thematic analysis of the information gathered from literature review. As per the research it can be concluded that the role of family, specialized teachers and schools for special education in educating blind children is crucial for their academic achievement, building good grades which would further contribute to their employment

INTRODUCTION

The Creation of Particular Learning Methods for Blind Children Education is a fundamental right for all individuals, regardless of their disabilities. However, for children with visual impairments, accessing education can be a challenge. Blindness or low vision can significantly hinder a child's ability to learn in the traditional classroom setting, making it crucial to develop specific learning methods that cater to their methods. In this essay, we will explore the creation of particular learning methods and the benefits of these methods.¹ The first step is creating specific learning methods for blind children is understanding the unique challenges they face in the classroom. Nowadays many children are unable to see like blindness so some teachers can face some kind of difficulties teaching them. This types of learning style can help study easily. And also, I really interesting in learning methods especially disability person. Blindness is an interesting style I choose because we can creative new style to teach children. It is necessary to devise unique instructional strategies for blind pupils. Blindness may greatly impair a child's capacity to study and it is vital to establish strategies that are especiy geared to assist these students. It is also important to develop ways thar are specifically designed to aid these children. Blindness students may be helped with their schoolwork in a variety of ways, inculding via the use of tactile learning, audio-based learning, and computer-based learning. In addition, students are able to improve their overall comprehension of the topic with the use of technology, which may give both auditory and tactile feedback.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Students who are blind may be given the opportunities an resources them. For instance, a child with a visual impairment struggle with reading, writing and even participating in a group activities. Therefore learning methods must be tailred to their unique needs corporating technology and other specialized resources. One of the most significant challenges in creating learning methods for blind children is to access to resources. Many schools lack the necessary resources, such a Brillie textbook, audio equipment and specialized software, to facilitate the learning process. Furthemore, the cost of acquiring these resources can be exorbitant, making

¹ Balan, O., Moldoveanu, A., & Moldoveanu, F. (2015). Navigational audio games: an effective approach toward improving spatial contextual learning for blind people.

it a challenge for schools with limited budgets to provide adequate support for blind children. Despite this challenges, there have been significant strides in developing specefic learning methods for blind children. One such method is the use of Braille.Braille is a system of raised dots that represent letters and numbers, allowing blind individuals to read and write². The use of Braille in the classroom enable children to learn to read and write opening up a whole new world of possibilities. Another significant development is the use of audio resources.Blind children can access audio books, podcasts, and other resources that can aid in the learning process. These resources can be accessed through specialized software and equipment, such as screen readers and text-to- speech software. Additionally, technology has played a significant role in creating specefic learning methods for blind children. Smatboards and other interactive technologies allow blind children to participate in a group activities, just like their sighted peers.

DISCUSSION

One of the significant benefit of these specific learning methods is the ability to foster independance and self-reliance. Blind children who learning to read and write from Braille can communicate and express themselves independantly,without relying on a sighted person to read or write for them. Furthemore, the use of audio resources and specialized technology empowers blind children to access materials independantly, allowing the to keep up with. Blindness is a handicap that may pose major challenges a child's capacity for education encountered by blind students through out the learning process, as well as the many approaches to education that may be taken significance of adding technology into the educational experience . The Obstacles That Blind Students Must Overcome Lack of access to visual informatsion is one of the most significant obstactacles that blind pupils must overcome. Students have a touch time comprehending the content that is being given to them it they are not provided with visual informatsion³.This is particularly true when it comes to mathematics and physic, both of which need the use of visual aids in order for the ideas to be comprehended. In addition, blind pupils may have trouble comprehending written content since they are unable to read the words and so are unable to grasp what they imply. Many Approaches to Education and Learning blind students have access to a wide range of educational opportunities and resources, which may significantly imrove their academic performance.Learning via touch or tactile learning is a popular approach for blind students it incorporates the use of real word items to facilitate the students comprahasion of abstract ideas encountered by blind students through out the learning process, as well as the many approaches to education that may be taken significance of adding technology into the educational experience . The Obstacles That Blind Students Must Overcome Lack of access to visual informatsion is one of the most significant obstactacles that blind pupils must overcome. Students have a touch time comprehending the content that is being given to them it they are not provided with visual informatsion.This is particularly true when it comes to mathematics and physic, both of which need the use of visual aids in order for the ideas to be comprehended. In addition, blind pupils

² Bedny, M., Richardson, H., & Saxe, R. (2015). “Visual” cortex responds to spoken language in blind children. *Journal of Neuroscience*

³ Bianco, S., Celona, L., Napoletano, P., &Schettini, R. (2018).On the use of deep learning for blind image quality assessment.*Signal, Image and Video Processing*

may have trouble comprehending written content since they are unable to read the words and so are unable to grasp what they imply. Many Approaches to Education and Learning blind students have access to a wide range of educational opportunities and resources, which may significantly improve their academic performance. Learning via touch or tactile learning is a popular approach for blind students it incorporates the use of real word items to facilitate the students comprehension of abstract ideas.

RESULTS.

While studying geometry, for instance, a student can benefit from using tactile board that has forms with raised edges. Blind pupils often make use audio- based learning as another typical way. This method includes playing audio recordings for the learner so that they may hear the information being taught rather than having to read it. Last but not least, kids who are blind may benefit from using computer - based learning thanks to the fact that particular programmes can be to meet their unique educational needs

Including Elements of Technology The significance of technology in today's classrooms is growing, and its value cannot be overstated, particularly for children who are visually impaired. Students who are visually impaired may get audible feedback via use of assistive technology, which will help them to have a deeper comprehension of the subject matter. In addition, many applications may be developed to be compatible with screen readers, which gives pupils access to the information they need. In conclusion, some systems may also⁴.

In this study, we will address the development of specific instructional strategies for visually impaired youngsters. Blindness is a handicap that may pose major challenges to challenges to a child's capacity for education. As a result, it is essential to establish educational strategies that are tailored precisely to the needs of pupils who are blind. In this study we will investigate the difficulties encountered by blind students throughout the learning process, as well as many approaches to education that may be taken and the significance of adding technology into the educational experience.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, creating specific learning methods for blind children is crucial in ensuring that they receive an education that meets their unique needs. While there are challenges, such as the lack of resources and high costs, significant strides have been made in developing Braille, audio resources, and specialized technology.

These methods not only empower blind children to learn independently but also foster inclusion and diversity in the classroom. Ultimately, by creating specific learning methods for blind children, we can ensure that they have access to the same opportunities as their sighted peers and reach their full potential.

It is important to note that individualized education plans (IEPs) are often developed for blind children to address their specific needs, strengths, and challenges. These plans involve collaboration among educators, parents and specialists to tailor learning methods and support services to the child's requirements, ensuring they receive a comprehensive and inclusive education.

⁴ Bianco, S., Celona, L., Napoletano, P., & Schettini, R. (2018). On the use of deep learning for blind image quality assessment. *Signal*

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